

Synthesis and characterisation of MgCr_2O_4 spinel precursor

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MgCr_2O_4 spinel was synthesized from Mg-Cr based hydrogels precursors prepared by coprecipitation technique. Ammonium hydroxide, ammonium carbonate and hexamethylene tetramine (HMT) used as different basic media for coprecipitation. Magnesium nitrate and ammonium dichromate were used as starting materials for the preparation of mixed solution containing Mg^{2+} and Cr^{3+} in molar ratio for $\text{MgO} : \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ as 1 : 1. It had been noticed that spinel formation was influenced by the mixed hydroxides precursors derived by using different basic precipitating agents. DTA, TGA, XRD, IR spectroscopy and SEM technique were utilized to characterize the coprecipitates as well as the final products generated by heat treatment of the coprecipitates at different temperatures. Thermal treatment of the coprecipitates led to the formation of MgCr_2O_4 spinel at low temperature (500°C). Mixed hydroxides derived by using ammonium hydroxide medium was the most effective one towards the formation of MgCr_2O_4 spinel at relatively low temperature.

MgCr_2O_4 possessing normal spinel structure, is an important refractory material because of its high melting point (2350°C), excellent resistance to slag attack, high temperature strength and high electrical resistivity. Moreover high purity MgCr_2O_4 has tremendous scope of use in electronic industries as bonding materials, sintering aids, emissive coating and high temperature stain. Various attempts have been made to synthesise the material at low temperature by different routes and coprecipitation technique appears promising for deriving the pure homogeneous precursors.

Anderson¹ studied the influence of oxygen activity on the sintering of MgCr_2O_4 and reported that densification of MgCr_2O_4 requires high temperature above 1700°C at $<10^{-6}$ atm. in oxygen partial pressure. Somiya *et al.*² investigated the phase relations in the system Cr_2O_3 -MgO- TiO_2 in air at 1400°C and observed Cr_2O_3 could be soluble up to 8 wt% into MgO in the Cr_2O_3 -MgO system and MgO was also soluble up to a certain percent in Cr_2O_3 but Cr_2O_3 and MgO could not enter into MgCr_2O_4 lattice to form solid solution. Lee and Sata³ worked on the oxygen partial pressure on vaporization rates in MgO- Cr_2O_3 system at 1600°C and reported that minimum rates of vaporization and the minimum vapour pressure were obtained at about 10^{-5} atm. of oxygen partial pressure at 1600°C for both Cr_2O_3 and MgCr_2O_4 . Again vacuum vaporization in the system MgO- Cr_2O_3 was studied at 1500 – 1700°C by Sata and Lee⁴ using

pure variety of MgO and Cr_2O_3 . The authors noticed that the phases in MgO- Cr_2O_3 system vaporize nearly congruently and the logarithm of the vaporization constant of MgCr_2O_4 increases linearly with increasing reciprocal temperature. Electrical behavior, micro structure and crystalline phases of MgCr_2O_4 - TiO_2 based porous ceramics were investigated by Nitta *et al.*⁵ using highly pure MgO, Cr_2O_3 and TiO_2 and they observed that the above system with inclusion of 30 mole % TiO_2 showed single phase solid solution with a pure MgCr_2O_4 type spinel structure. Yamaguchi and Okamura⁶ investigated the densification of MgCr_2O_4 - TiO_2 content and temperature with decreasing oxygen partial pressure. When heated in carbon powder bed MgCr_2O_4 with more than 20 mole % of TiO_2 offered a relative density of $\geq 95\%$. They also reported that a new compound viz. $9\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{MgO} \cdot 5\text{Ti}_2\text{O}_3$ was formed due to reaction between MgCr_2O_4 and TiO_2 in the range of more than 30 mole % of TiO_2 during heating in carbon powder. Park and Kim⁷ reported that electrical conductivity of MgO-doped Cr_2O_3 within the solubility limit was increased with MgO content due to creation of holes and annihilation of chromium vacancies and the same was decreased above solubility limit with increasing MgO content due to the formation of MgCr_2O_4 spinel phase. Yoshida *et al.*⁸ studied the formation process of MgCr_2O_4 prepared by hydrazine method. The authors used magnesium chloride, chromium chloride

and hydrazine monohydrate as starting materials. Finally the authors reported that dense MgCr₂O₄ ceramics with 99.55% theoretical density could be made possible by introducing plasma sintering procedure at 1400°C for 5 min and 30 MPa. Sintering of MgCr₂O₄ was also done by Moriwake *et al.*^{9,10} at various holding times. The authors observed that all the samples had a single phase spinel structure and were p-type semiconductors. The lattice constant was increased with increasing the holding time and electrical resistivity was divided into two groups according to the difference of holding time.

The present work is an attempt to generate pure micro-fine particles of co-precipitated hydrogel of definite molar ratio for MgO-Cr₂O₃ system with respect to variation of basic media and reaction conditions followed by in depth study of spinelization behavior of coprecipitated hydrogel precursors during heat treatment.

Results and discussion

Divalent character of magnesium is only common while chromium possesses variable valencies. Again the complete precipitation of magnesium occurs at pH 12.0 whereas pH 8.0 is required for the precipitation of chromium. Moreover, the only Cr³⁺ state is required for precipitation of chromium which can be obtained by reduction of 6+ state of chromium to 3+ state by using hydrogen peroxide or a mixture of methyl alcohol and sulphuric acid. The use of excess methyl alcohol as reducing agent in presence of sulphuric acid ensures the complete reduction of Cr⁶⁺ to Cr³⁺ state from ammonium dichromate and was practiced in this study.

Individual hydroxide gels and mixed hydroxides gels of magnesium and chromium were prepared by addition of different basic medium to the salt solution containing Mg²⁺ Cr³⁺ ions at pH 7.5–11.3. During mixed hydroxide gel formation (MCH-1 to MCH-3), no abnormality was noticed in relation to opacity but different color of coprecipitated hydrogels viz. light gray (MCH-1), bluish green (MCH-2), greenish blue (MCH-3) respectively were observed, which might be related to varying degree of precipitation of Mg²⁺ ions at lower pH ranges followed during the coprecipitation process by different basic media. The pH values of the gels due to the addition of different basic media and the average particle size of the gel powder in aqueous media are given Table 1.

The variation of average particle size of the coprecipitated MgO-Cr₂O₃ hydrogel in relation to different

basic media appears insignificant due to possible agglomeration during its formation.

Table 1. pH of the medium and average particle size of the gel powders

Sample no.	pH of the medium	Average particle size (µm)
M-1	11.25	0.330
C-1	7.55	0.298
MCH-1	8.45	0.301
MCH-2	8.99	0.304
MCH-3	9.00	0.290

The DTA and TGA curves of the powders were shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. The system M-1 contained Mg(OH)₂, the decomposition of which had started at 350°C^{11,12}. DTA curve showed a sharp endothermic effect from 340 to 429°C. This was due to dehydroxylation of Mg(OH)₂. The TG curve also showed a steep weight loss in this temperature region. The system C-1 contained hydrous oxide of Cr³⁺ having indefinite composition i.e. Cr₂O₃.xH₂O, although it is frequently referred as chromic hydroxide Cr(OH)₃^{13,14}. The endothermic effects at 184, 300 and 386°C were due to dehydration of hydrous oxide and corresponding three steps weight loss were also observed from the TG curve. Jovitschitsch¹⁴ reported that hydrated chromic oxide readily absorbed carbon dioxide from the atmosphere forming [Cr₂(OH)₅]₂CO₃.8H₂O. So the exothermic peak at 413°C might be due to decarboxylation of carbonated hydroxy compound. TG curve also showed weight loss at this temperature region (400 to 453°C). MCH-1, MCH-2 and MCH-3 contained mainly mix hydroxides of magnesium and chromium. In the system MCH-1 broad endo effect from 277 to 404°C was due to dehydroxylation of mix hydroxide. MCH-2 showed endo effects at 190, 200, 268 and 460°C whereas MCH-3 showed endo effects at 176, 286 and 486°C. Dehydration of mix hydroxide at different temperature might be due to poor homogeneity followed by partial separation of individual phases. Corresponding weight loss was also noticed from the TG curves of the said systems. Yoshida *et al.*⁸ reported that the gel powder obtained by hydrazine method at pH 9 showed a sharp exotherm at 480–530°C and finally the authors concluded that this exo effect was due to formation of MgCr₂O₄ spinel at that temperature region. In case of MCH-2 and MCH-3 exo effect had been observed from 465 to 472°C and 470 to 490°C respectively. TG curves of these two system showed weight loss at these regions. So it may be inferred that these exo effects might due to decarboxylation of carbonated hydroxy phase of chromium compound¹⁴ formed owing to the separation of hydrous chromic oxide during the course of gel powder preparation.

Fig. 1. DTA curves of the dried hydrogel powders (M-1 to MCH-3).

XRD patterns of the gel powder dried at 110°C and heat treated at different temperature were shown in Fig. 3. M-1 gel powder obtained from Mg^{2+} (nitrate) solution using NH_4OH solution as basic medium showed well defined crystalline peak of $Mg(OH)_2$ (brucite) whereas C-1 obtained from Cr^{3+} (sulphate) solution using the same NH_4OH solution as basic medium showed amorphous character. All the other gel powders viz. MCH-1, MCH-2 and MCH-3 obtained from the mix solution (Mg^{2+} and Cr^{3+}) using different basic media viz. NH_4OH , $NH_4OH-(NH_4)_2CO_3$ and $NH_4OH-HMT$ also showed amorphous nature. So, it might be concluded that in case of mixed hydroxide coprecipitation $Mg(OH)_2$ did not crystallize and amorphous mixed hydroxide were formed.

All the mixed hydroxides (MCH-1, MCH-2 and MCH-3) were subjected to heat treatment at 500°C (referred as

Fig. 2. TGA curves of the dried hydrogel powders (M-1 to MCH-3).

Fig. 3. XRD patterns of the hydrogel powders dried at 110°C (M-1 to MCH-3).

MC-15, MC-25 and MC-35 respectively) and 800°C (referred as MC-18, MC-28 and MC-38 respectively) for 2 h and the patterns were shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 respectively. In case of MC-15 and MC-18 the only crystalline phase of $MgCr_2O_4$ was noticed but in case of MC-25, MC-28, MC-35 and MC-38 the major phase corresponded to $MgCr_2O_4$ along with minor amount of Cr_2O_3 . In case of MCH-1 where NH_4OH was used as basic medium maximum homogeneity occurred during the course of

Fig. 4. XRD patterns of the hydrogel powders (MC-15, MC-25 and MC-35) heat treated at 500°C.

coprecipitation of mixed hydroxide but in case of other two systems viz. MCH-2 and MCH-3 where $\text{NH}_4\text{OH}-(\text{NH}_2)_2\text{CO}_3$ and $\text{NH}_4\text{OH-HMT}$ were used as basic media respectively, some portion of individual component separated out and as a result partial heterogeneity occurred. During heat treatment this separated phase crystallised and showed its individual character (Cr_2O_3). These facts were also confirmed by DTA and TGA, that in case of MCH-2

Fig. 5. XRD patterns of the hydrogel powders (MC-18, MC-28 and MC-38) heat treated at 800°C .

Fig. 6. IR spectra of the hydrogel powders (MC-18, MC-28 and MC-38) heat treated at 800°C .

and MCH-3 exo effects were noticed at 465 to 472°C and 472 to 490°C might be due to expulsion of carbon dioxide owing to the formation of $[\text{Cr}_2(\text{OH})_5]_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}^{14}$ like compound and corresponding weight loss was also showed by TG curves at this temperature region.

IR spectra of the mixed hydroxide gel powders heat treated at 800°C for 2 h were shown in Fig. 6. The bands around 645 , 535 and 427 cm^{-1} which could be correlated with spinel structure^{15,16}. Maximum intense peak was noticed in case of MC-18 where NH_4OH was used as basic medium for the preparation of mixed hydroxide. This fact was also supported by X-ray studies.

Fig. 7 showed SEM micrograph of powdered sample (MC-18) heat treated at 800°C for 2 h. It was observed that the particles were spherical shaped with sizes varying from 0.20 to $0.30\text{ }\mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 7. SEM micrograph of MgCr_2O_4 powder (MC-18) heat treated at 800°C .

Conclusion :

Mg-Cr based hydroxy compounds were prepared using different basic media for the synthesis of MgCr_2O_4 spinel at low temperature. Results were summarised as follows :

- (1) Thermal analysis and XRD patterns showed that coprecipitated gel powders were not a mixture of individual hydroxide.
- (2) Basic media played an important role during the preparation of precursor hydroxy compound used for obtaining MgCr_2O_4 spinel at low temperature.
- (3) XRD patterns showed that spinel formation took place at around 500°C and the best result was noticed by the coprecipitate (MCH-1) using NH_4OH as basic medium.
- (4) Spinel formation was further confirmed by IR spectroscopic analysis.
- (5) Derived spinel powder (800°C) were spherical in shape (MC-18) with sizes ranging from 0.20 to $0.30\text{ }\mu\text{m}$.

Experimental

Raw materials : Reagent grade ammonium dichromate $[(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7]$, magnesium nitrate $[\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ were used as starting materials. For the preparation of basic media laboratory reagent grade ammonium hydroxide

(NH₄OH), ammonium carbonate [(NH₄)₂CO₃] and hexamethylene tetramine [(CH₂)₆N₄] referred as HMT were used. Reduction of Cr⁶⁺ of ammonium dichromate to Cr³⁺ was performed by interaction of analytical grade methyl alcohol (CH₃OH) and sulphuric acid.

Basic media : Three types of basic media viz. [1] ammonium hydroxide diluted with water (1 : 1), [2] 0.01 mole (NH₄)₂CO₃ per 100 ml of ammonium hydroxide solution (1 : 1) and [3] 0.01 mole (CH₂)₆N₄(HMT) per 100 ml of ammonium hydroxide solution (1 : 1) were used for the preparation of different mixed hydroxides gel powders.

Table 2. Referred systems, precursor salt solutions, basic media and end product during the preparation of gel powders

Referred system	Precursor salt solution	Basic medium	End product
M-1	Mg ²⁺ (nitrate)	NH ₄ OH	Mg(OH) ₂
C-1	Cr ³⁺ (sulphate)	NH ₄ OH	Cr(OH) ₃
MCH-1	Mg ²⁺ (nitrate) + Cr ³⁺ (sulphate)	NH ₄ OH	Mg-Cr hydroxide
MCH-2	-do-	NH ₄ OH-(NH ₄) ₂ CO ₃	Mg-Cr hydroxide
MCH-3	-do-	NH ₄ OH-(CH ₂) ₆ N ₄	Mg-Cr hydroxide

Preparation of gel powders :

0.1 M Mg²⁺ solution was taken in a jar and ammonium hydroxide solution (1 : 1) was added gradually with stirring until gelation was completed. The gel formed was allowed to age for 24 h followed by filtration, washing with distilled water, vacuum drying at 50°C and pulverisation. Following the same procedure using Cr³⁺ solutions and ammonium hydroxide solution (1 : 1) as basic medium, hydrous chromium hydroxide gel powder was also prepared. For the preparation of mixed hydroxides gel powder, mixed solution containing 0.1 M Mg²⁺ and 0.1 M Cr³⁺ solution were taken in a jar and warmed at 60 to 80°C. Corresponding basic medium were introduced in the same manner following same procedure as mentioned above. Outline for the preparation individual and mixed hydroxide gel powders with various basic media are shown in Schemes 1 and 2 and referred systems, precursor salt solutions, corresponding basic medium and end products were shown in Table 1.

Characterisation :

Thermal behaviour of the gel powders were studied by differential thermal analysis and thermogravimetric analysis using Shimadzu DT-50 equipment with a heating rate of 10°C per minute. Gel powders were also subjected to heat treatment at different temperatures and the resultant phases were identified by X-ray diffraction technique using Philips defractometer, PW1734 instrument with Ni filtered CuK_α, 40 kV and 20 mA radiation. Mixed hydroxides gel powders

Scheme 1. Preparation of individual hydroxide gel powders.

Scheme 2. Preparation of mixed hydroxide gel powders.

heat treated at 800°C were subjected to IR spectroscopic analysis using Perkin-Elmer FTIR 1615 equipment. Shape and size of heat treated powders were investigated utilizing SEM technique using LEO-S4301, U.K. equipment.

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